

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 1-ARYL-2-MERCAPTOBENZOYL SUBSTITUTED IMIDAZOLE(III)

No.	X	Y	A.				P.		G.
			<i>niger</i>	<i>terreus</i>	<i>nidulans</i>	<i>tenuis</i>	<i>funiculosum</i>	<i>lunata</i>	
1	Control		++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	
2	H	H	+±	++	+±	+	++	+±	
3	H	NO ₂	-	±	±	-	++	+±	
4	2-CH ₃	H	+++	+±	++	+++	-	-	
5	3-CH ₃	H	+++	+++	+±	++++	+++	++++	
6	3-CH ₃	NO ₂	-	±	+±	-	-	±	
7	4-CH ₃	H	++	++	+±	+±	++	+±	
8	4-CH ₃	NO ₂	+	+	+±	+±	+±	+	
9	2-OCH ₃	H	++	+++	+++	+++	++	+±	
10	4-OCH ₃	H	++	+++	++++	++	+	++	
11	4-OCH ₃	NO ₂	-	+±	+	+±	+	+	
12	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	H	+++	++++	++++	++++	+++	++++	
13	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	NO ₂	-	-	+	±	-	±	
14	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	+	++	+±	+±	++	+	
15	4-OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	++	+±	++	+++	+±	±	
16	4-Cl	H	++	+±	++	+±	+	±	
17	4-Cl	NO ₂	±	-	+	-	-	+	

++ to +++ = Good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.
 ± to +± = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.
 - to - = No growth, fungicidal activity.

Results and Discussion

All the synthesised 1-aryl-2-mercaptobenzoyl substituted imidazoles were tested for amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution ; compound Nos. 2, 5, 11 and 13 showed good amoebicidal activity and compound Nos. 1, 9, 10 and 15 showed less amoebicidal activity, compounds 2, 5, 11 and 15 were found to possess good fungicidal activity and 7, 9 and 14 were slight fungicidal in nature.

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References

1. P. MELLONI, E. DRADI and W. LONGMANN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 926.
2. C. COSAN, R. CRISON, R. N. HORCLOIS and J. J. ROBERT, *Arz. forzua.*, 1966, 16, 23.
3. R. RAFFER and V. SUNFIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 934.
4. P. B. BUDD and H. TOLKONOLY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 794.
5. P. C. SRIVASTAVA and D. G. STREELA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, 18, 530.
6. M. L. GARG and A. K. MANAVA, *Current Science*, 1976, 45, 647.
7. L. DROBNICA, M. Z. PLENIAC and K. ANTOS, *Microbiol.*, 1967, 15, 701.
8. A. L. JHONSON and D. C. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 1524.
9. A. L. JHONSON and D. C. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1974, 17, 46.
10. A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry by I.L. VOGEL, E. L. B. S. Edition, London, 1971, p. 796.
11. R. C. GUPTA, R. NATH, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHOR, *Indian J. Pharmacy*, 1977, 39, 111.

Studies on Spiro Compounds. Part I
 Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of
 Optically Active L(+)-1-Arylaza-4-thia-6-
 isopropyl-9-methylspiro [4.5]-decane-2-ones

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MENTHONE derivatives and thiazolidinones possess wide variety of therapeutic activity, e.g., anthelmintic¹, bacteriostatic², hypnotic³, anaesthetic⁴ and antifungal⁵. We have now synthesised optically active spirothiazolidinones of type (I)* by condensing 1-menthone with different amines and thio-glycolic acid⁶ in order to study their pharmaceutical activity. The constitution of spirothiazolidinones was supported by the infra-red spectra study^{7,8}. The infra-red spectra of spirothiazolidinones in KBr exhibited bands at 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and 1560 cm⁻¹ (CO-N<). The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

(I)

R = Aryl

* The disposition of the C-S and C-N bonds in the spiro compound is unknown.

TABLE—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE SPIROTHIAZOLIDINONES OF TYPE-I

Sr.	R	Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Dimethylformamide c(1,1)	[α] _D ²⁰ °	% of Nitrogen		Diameter of the zone of inhibition in mm		
							Found	Cal.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NOS	53	159-61	2.00	+3.5	4.5	4.62	11	10	10
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	41	152-54	3.00	+3.0	4.35	4.41	10	10	10
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	48	158-60	1.50	+2.3	4.5	4.41	14	16	17
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	48	180-82	2.00	+3.5	4.45	4.41	11	14	23
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	51	108-10	2.40	+3.4	4.3	4.20	17	13	22
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	38	150-52	2.30	+2.6	4.3	4.20	15	11	10
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	60	169-71	2.00	+3.5	4.25	4.20	18	15	12
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	53	112-14	2.50	+2.4	4.1	4.15	25	14	25
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	50	172-74	2.50	+2.8	4.2	4.15	21	12	18
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	58	178-80	2.00	+4.0	4.2	4.15	16	13	22

Experimental

(a) Preparation of (-)-menthone⁹ :

(-)-Menthone was prepared by the oxidation of (-)-menthol [α]_D¹⁸ - 50.1° (ethanol) by potassium dichromate solution and had [α]_D²⁰ - 24.8°, d_4^{20} = 0.8954.

(b) Preparation of 1-phenylaza-4-thia-6-isopropyl-9-methylspiro[4,5]-decane-2-one :

A mixture of (-)-menthone (3.18 g; 0.02 mole), aniline (1.95 g; 0.02 mole) and anhydrous benzene (10 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 6 hrs. Thioglycolic acid (4 ml; 80%) and anhydrous sodium sulphate were then added and contents were refluxed further for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from aqueous ethanol after the removal of benzene and unreacted thioglycolic acid, yield 52%, m.p. 159-61° (Found C = 71.0, H = 8.0, N = 4.50; C₁₈H₂₅NOS, requires C = 71.31, H = 8.25, N = 4.62).

Similarly other bases were condensed. The physical constants are recorded in Table.

Antimicrobial Screening

The purified products were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method¹⁰ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e., *Staphylococcus aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e., *Escherichia coli*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 10 mg/ml. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded (Table). *o*- and *m*-Chlorophenylaza derivatives were highly active while *o*-anisyl, *p*-anisyl and *p*-chlorophenylaza derivatives were moderately active against *S. aureus*. *m*-Tolylaza derivative possess good activity against *E. coli* while other products were normally active.

The antifungal activity was tested against *Aspergillus niger* by cup-plate method. *p*-tolyl, *o*-anisyl, *o*- and *p*-chlorophenylaza derivatives possessed

very good antifungal activity while *m*-tolyl and *m*-chlorophenylaza derivatives were moderately active.

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References

1. Y. NOZAVA, *Sapparo Med. J.*, 1952, 3, 48.
2. Y. SATCURAL and H. KANAI, *Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1953, 1, 337.
3. J. DORAN and H. A. SHONLE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 3, 193.
4. H. D. TROUTMANN and M. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3436.
5. R. H. MOZZONI and P. C. EAMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 3471.
6. B. K. RAVAL and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 353.
7. RANDALL, et al: "Infrared Determination of Organic Structures". D. VAN Nostrand Company, Inc., New York, 1949.
8. I. BENGHIAT: U. S. pat. 2,905, 689 (1959).
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry". Third Edition p. 337.
10. S. P. HIREMUTH, M. G. PUROHIT and M. SIRAI, *Karnatak Uni. J. of Sci.*, 1974, 19, 208.

Chemical Examination of *Daphne oleoides*

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DAPHNE *oleoides* which belongs to the family Thymelaeaceae is highly poisonous. The roots of the plant are purgative while its barks and leaves are used in cutaneous afflictions¹. Literature survey